

Novel mycelium-based biocomposites from nutshell particles produced through a bioprocess engineering approach combining liquid- and solid-state fermentation

Štěpán Hýsek^{1,2,*}, Paraskevi Charalambous³, Christoph Preimesberger^{2,4}, Luboš Prokúpek⁵, Notburga Gierlinger^{3,*}, Rupert Wimmer^{2,6}

1 - Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of Life Science Prague, Kamýcká 129, Prague, 165 00, Czech Republic

2 - BOKU University, Institute of Wood Technology and Renewable Materials, Department of Natural Sciences and Sustainable Resources, Konrad-Lorenz-Straße 24, 3430 Tulln, Austria

3 - BOKU University, Institute of Biophysics, Department of Natural Sciences and Sustainable Resources, Muthgasse 11, 1190 Vienna, Austria

4 - Wood K plus - Competence Center for Wood Composites & Wood Chemistry, Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH, Altenberger Straße 69, A-4040 Linz, Austria

5 - Institute of Chemistry and Technology of Macromolecular Materials, Faculty of Chemical Technology, University of Pardubice, Studentská 573, 532 10 Pardubice, Czech Republic

6 - Department of Wood Science and Technology, Faculty of Forestry and Wood Technology, Mendel University in Brno, Zemědělská 1, 613 00 Brno, Czech Republic

*Corresponding author: burgi.gierlinger@boku.ac.at; hyseks@fd.czu.cz

Abstract

This study presents the development and characterisation of mycelium-based biocomposites (MBBs) reinforced with ground walnut and pistachio nutshells. A combined liquid- and solid-state fermentation process employing *Ganoderma sessile* was used to bind the lignocellulosic particles without synthetic adhesives. The influence of nut species and glycerol treatment on composite properties was studied. Results showed that walnut-based MBBs exhibited higher stiffness and Shore A hardness compared to pistachio-based variants, with the glycerol-treated walnut MBB reaching the highest mechanical performance. DVS analysis confirmed reduced

moisture uptake and hysteresis in glycerol-treated samples. SEM revealed a dense hyphal network interconnecting nutshell particles and a surface fungal skin. FTIR spectra indicated compositional differences related to lignin and chitin content, while STA revealed typical thermal decomposition profiles of lignocellulosic composites with additional degradation stages attributed to glycerol. Results showed that walnut-based MBBs exhibited higher stiffness and Shore A hardness compared to pistachio-based variants, with the glycerol-treated walnut MBB reaching the highest mechanical performance. Its Shore A hardness was 71.4, compared to 63.8 in the untreated pistachio MBB. DVS analysis confirmed reduced equilibrium moisture content in glycerol-treated samples and a decrease in hysteresis. STA showed a residual mass of 25.6% and main DTG peaks at 300.6 °C and 354.6 °C for the glycerol-treated walnut MBB, compared to 29.9% residual mass and main DTG peaks at 281.5 °C and 335.1 °C for the untreated pistachio variant. FTIR spectra indicated higher lignin-associated absorbance in walnut composites, consistent with their mechanical performance.

Keywords: composite material, mycelium, walnut, pistachio, fermentation

1. Introduction

Mycelium-based biocomposites (MBB) are composite materials from lignocellulosic (LC) raw materials bonded with fungal fibres. As mycelium is used in order to interconnect the LC particles, no adhesives are used for bonding the composite material (Muiruri et al. 2023). Mycelium, the living organism, can be understood as a big advantage in the process of material production. The living mycelium in certain stages of material production or material use provides a possibility of material partial regeneration during MBB production and even potential regeneration of damaged mycelium during product use. These abilities can finally prolong materials' life cycle and significantly influence its functional properties (Elsacker et al. 2021; Sandak 2023).

LC raw material used for MBB production is mostly wood or straw and represents the main substrate component for MBB (Alaneme et al. 2023). Additionally, agricultural residues

from cotton production, hemp straw and seeds, flax shives, kenaf fibres, sugarcane bagasse or rice husks were successfully used in substrates for MBB production since they are rich in cellulose, lignin or lower molecular-weight sugars (Sydor et al. 2021). These agricultural residues are also commonly utilised as reinforcing fillers or matrix components in other types of biocomposites (Hýsek et al. 2016; Gajdačová et al. 2018; Němec et al. 2025). Other valuable sources of LC biomass are nutshell particles, which have been previously used for the production of various types of composites (Sutivisedsak et al. 2012; Dong et al. 2017; Zhang and Yu 2022; Sahin et al. 2024), but not yet for the production of MBB. Nutshells are not only composed of fibres, but also thick-walled lignified sclerenchyma cells of different shape (Huss et al. 2020; Huss and Gierlinger 2021). Among the different nutshells, walnut and pistachio shells stand out by being solely composed of polylobate puzzle cells (Antreich et al. 2019, Xiao et al. 2021). Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of LC fillers such as walnut and pistachio shells in composite materials due to their mechanical stiffness, lignin content, and availability as agro-industrial by-products. Karagöz et al. (2024) showed that walnut shell powder significantly enhances the stiffness and thermal stability of HDPE composites (Karagöz et al. 2024). From a broader engineering perspective, the erosion resistance of walnut shell composites was investigated by Sepetcioglu et al. (2025), showing that walnut fillers can improve surface durability and dimensional stability (Sepetcioglu et al. 2025). Finally, Sepet et al. (2020) discussed scale-up challenges and processing behaviour of shell-filled composites, confirming their feasibility for large-scale applications (Sepet et al., 2020).

Solid-state fermentation is widely used to manufacture MBB. This method is based on LC substrate colonisation with fungal mycelium. To produce particles or fibres for substrates, LC raw materials have to be disintegrated, and the substrate is further hydrated with water and sterilised or pasteurised, usually with heat. After this heat treatment, the substrate is ready to be inoculated by the selected fungus. Fungi used for MBB production are wood-decaying fungi that are able to decompose lignin, cellulose, and hemicelluloses. Therefore, LC substrate serves as a source of nutrition for fungus and provides it with enough nutrients to build a

network of fungal fibres that interconnect the particles. When the mycelium colonizes the substrate, the LC substrate is, however, not fully degraded and, therefore, provides structural stability to the MBB (Attias et al. 2020; Elsacker et al. 2020; Sydor et al. 2021). The properties of MBB are substantially affected by the fungus used (Appels et al. 2019). The resulting MBB properties are, however, not the only criteria used for the selection of fungus. Growth rate, resistance to contamination and undemanding growth conditions have also to be considered. The most suitable fungal species for the production of MBB, therefore, belong to the *Pleurotus* genus, followed by *Ganoderma* and *Trametes* (Aiduang et al. 2022; Cerimi et al. 2019).

This production method based on solid-state fermentation provides MBB with porous structure characterised by density ranging mostly from 110 kg/m³ to 330 kg/m³, thermal conductivity comparable to the commonly used thermal insulation materials (0.05 - 0.07 W/m.K) and great acoustic absorption properties. However, the composites are soft, characterised by low mechanical properties and high water absorption (Alaneme et al. 2023; Madusanka et al. 2024). For instance, MBB produced by the mycelium of *P. ostreatus* grown on straw substrate reached a compressive strength of 0.02 MPa; when grown on the substrate from oak sawdust, the compressive strength was 0.15 MPa (Ghazvinian et al. 2019). The bending strength of MBB produced from wood particles enriched with cellulose nanofibers (CNF) was 3.5 MPa (Sun et al. 2019) and the tensile strength of MBB from wood sawdust was reported to be from 0.05 MPa to 0.18 MPa, whereas the composites grown on straw reached substantially lower tensile strength (Jones et al. 2020). All studies clearly confirmed that the mechanical properties are influenced mainly by MBB density, size of particles used and fungal strain (Sydor et al. 2021; Alaneme et al. 2023).

The water absorption rate of MBB ranges from 40% to 580% and is affected by substrate composition, manufacturing parameters, and method of measurement (Attias et al. 2020; Madusanka et al. 2024). Besides this, the surface of MBB strongly affects the water absorption rate. In the case that strong mycelium, called fungal skin, is formed on the surface of the sample, the water absorption dramatically decreases. However, given the hydrophilic

properties of LC substrates used for MBB production, the bulk of not modified MBB is always reported to be hydrophilic, which also determines MBB durability and biodegradability (Hýsek et al. 2023; Madusanka et al. 2024).

Liquid-state fermentation has already been employed in order to produce pure mycelium (fungal skin). As the fungal skin is grown on the surface of the liquid culture, the advantage of this method is that it enables the production of pure mycelium without mixing the mycelium with LC substrate (Appels et al. 2018; Appels et al. 2020; Sayfutdinova et al. 2023). However, no approach has been reported in scientific papers so far where liquid-state fermentation is used to bond LC particles with mycelium and subsequently bond a composite.

The objective of this study was to develop MBB from pistachio and walnut nutshell particles using an innovative method composed of a combination of solid- and liquid-state fermentation. We hypothesise that the used production method (as depicted in Figure 1) provides the novel MBB with a nature-inspired structure, resulting in MBB with unique properties compared to the current state of the art. The novelty of this study therefore lies in the use of a two-step bioprocess combining liquid-state fermentation for initial colonisation of LC particles, followed by solid-state fermentation for final composite formation. To the best of our knowledge, this hybrid approach has not yet been reported in the context of MBBs. Most prior studies rely exclusively on solid-state fermentation, where fungal colonisation and composite shaping occur simultaneously in a form. In contrast, our method enables uniform mycelial coverage of ground particles during liquid-state fermentation, enhancing fungal–particle integration.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Pistachio (*Pistacia vera*) and walnut (*Juglans regia*) nutshell particles with a particle size lower than 100 micrometres were used in order to produce mycelium-based biocomposites and the selected strain was *Ganoderma sessile* (“North Blair”, Terrestrial Fungi,

USA). The shape and dimensions of the lignocellulosic particles are characterised using SEM in the Results and Discussion section. Malt extract (ME) was purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG, Germany, and a 2% water solution of ME (2%ME) was used in order to produce liquid culture as well as liquid inoculum. Glycerol ($\geq 99\%$) was purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG, Germany. Malt extract agar (MAE) was purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG, Germany and was used in order to cultivate the cultures on agar placed in Petri dishes.

2.2 Methods

MBB production

Five squares (5 mm x 5 mm in dimensions) of mycelium grown on MEA were shaken (150 rpm) with 200 ml 2%ME at 22°C for 13 days in order to prepare the liquid inoculum of *G. sessile*. Liquid cultures were prepared by inoculation of 200 ml 2%ME by 40 ml of inoculum, and the cultures were cultivated at 20°C for 7 days by constant shaking at 150 rpm. After 7 days, 5% (dry weight/volume) of ground nutshells were added to the liquid culture and shaken at the same condition for another 4 days. After this period, 40 g of the culture was filtered using a polyethylene (PE) filter with pores 29 μm in diameter, the pressure during filtration was 20 mbar. The filter cake was placed on a petri dish and lightly covered in order to allow air to enter the petri dish and enable further metabolic activity of the mycelium. This experiment design enabled an additional 7-day-long solid-state fermentation, after which the growing composite was turned over in order to allow the mycelium to grow properly on both sides. After another 7 days, the composites were fully grown, and the growth was terminated by vacuum drying at 70°C and 700 mbar for 2 days. In order to determine the dry mass of the produced composites, all samples were oven-dried at 103°C. This procedure resulted in the production of particle-based composites bonded with a mycelium non-woven structure, consisting of interconnected fungal hyphae forming a porous fibrous network; the weight per unit area of the resulting composites from walnut shell particles was 1035 g/m², composites from pistachio nutshells reached 935 g/m² and reference without nutshell particles 230 g/m². The mycelium-based biocomposites were treated with glycerol. Glycerol treatment was conducted as immersion of

the samples in 20% water solution of glycerol for 96 hours at 20°C. The list of produced variants is provided in Table 1, and the production method of a nature-inspired composite structure is depicted in Figure 1.

Table 1 Variants of mycelium-based biocomposites

Variant	Nutshell	Treatment
W0	Walnut	-
WG	Walnut	Glycerol
P0	Pistachio	-
PG	Pistachio	Glycerol
R0	-	-
RG	-	Glycerol

Figure 1 The production method of a nature-inspired composite structure, ground nutshells colonised with mycelium during liquid-state fermentation (A), produced MBB at the end of the solid-state fermentation (B), final inner structure of the produced MBB (C)

Dynamic Vapour Sorption (DVS)

Sorption/desorption isotherms were determined using a DVS Advantage apparatus (Surface Measurement Systems Ltd., London, United Kingdom). All measurements were conducted at a constant temperature of 25 °C. The measurement program is illustrated in Figure 2A. Briefly, the samples were initially pre-dried at 0% relative humidity (RH) for 9 hours. Following this, the

RH was increased in 20% increments, each maintained for 3 hours, until reaching 100% RH. The duration of 3 hours per RH step was selected based on preliminary trials, during which the sample mass was continuously monitored to ensure that equilibrium was reached. These tests confirmed that the mass of the MBB samples remained constant after 3 hours. The desorption cycle followed the same steps in reverse, decreasing the RH in 20% increments from 100% back to 0%.

Figure 2 The measurement program for sorption/desorption isotherms determination (A), the measurement program used in STA experiments (B)

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) was conducted using DMA 303 Explexor (Netzsch, Selb, Germany). The samples were tested using a compression mode, the frequency was 1 Hz, the dynamic deformation was 0.03 mm, the dynamic force was 10 N, and the static force was 13 N. These parameters were selected based on preliminary optimisation to ensure stable contact, low signal noise, and conditions representative of standard viscoelastic testing of lignocellulosic composites. Compression mode was selected due to the brittleness of the tested MBBs, which made bending and tensile modes unfeasible. The tested temperature interval was from 20°C to 230°C with an increment of 3°C/min. The upper temperature limit of 230 °C was selected to cover the full functional range of the materials, including the onset of thermal degradation, in order to evaluate their thermal stability and performance limits. The tested MBB samples had dimensions of 5 mm × 5 mm × 1 mm (length × width × thickness). In

contrast, the reference samples R0 and RG were significantly thinner, and it was not feasible to test a single layer of these materials. Therefore, these samples for DMA were prepared by stacking five layers of R0 and RG to achieve comparable thickness. It should be noted that this layered structure differs from the structure of the MBB samples containing nutshell particles. This structural difference must be taken into account when interpreting the DMA results.

Shore Hardness

Shore hardness was measured using a Shore durometer (PTC Instruments, USA), based on the EN ISO 868 method. Shore A method with a flattened tip of the indenter was employed. Although the Shore A method is primarily intended for testing flexible materials, it was employed in this study because the produced composites were brittle, and alternative hardness testing methods led to material chipping. Each variant was measured 10 times. While Shore A hardness is typically used for elastomers, it was employed here due to the brittle nature of the developed MBBs, which precluded other methods. The results are used solely to compare hardness among the different MBB variants and are not benchmarked against standard elastomeric materials. Although EN ISO 868 recommends a minimum sample thickness of 4 mm, the tested MBB specimens had a final thickness of approximately 1 mm due to fabrication constraints. All hardness measurements were therefore performed on single-layer samples under identical conditions, and the obtained values serve as relative indicators of surface hardness among the developed MBB.

Simultaneous Thermal Analysis (STA)

The thermal decomposition behaviour of the material was analysed by simultaneous thermal analysis (STA) using a Netzsch STA 409 PG under pyrolytic conditions with a nitrogen flow of 60 mL/min. Prior to measurement, the sample was ground to a particle size below 0.5 mm using a Retsch Ultra Centrifugal Mill ZM 200 with a rotational speed of 10000 rpm and a 0.5 mm mesh sieve. The analysis was performed in two steps. In the first step, the sample was

heated to 105 °C, followed by a 10-minute isothermal drying phase. Afterward, the sample was cooled to 20 °C using liquid nitrogen. In the second step, the material was heated to 600 °C at a heating rate of 10 K/min. An illustration of the measurement program can be found in Figure 2B.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR)

To conclude on differences in the chemical composition of the films, FT- IR spectra were acquired with 32 scans using an ATR-unit attached to an FT-IR spectrometer (Vertex 70, Bruker, Billerica, USA). The dry samples were milled to have a homogeneous mixture and four spectra measured, averaged and cut to the most relevant wavenumber range from 1800 cm⁻¹ to 850 cm⁻¹ using OPUS 7.5 software (Bruker, USA).

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM was performed to examine the architecture of the composites. The samples were gold sputtered (4nm) with a sputter coater (LEICA EM SCD005). High-vacuum secondary electron imaging was performed using an Apreo VS SEM (Thermo Scientific, The Netherlands) at 5 and 10 kV and 0.10 nA current, using the OptiPlan use case, detector T1, and mode A+B. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) using an Xplore 15 EDX detector (Oxford Instruments, Great Britain) was performed to monitor surface elemental composition.

3. Results and discussion

Dynamic Vapour Sorption

The untreated MBB from walnut and pistachio nutshells exhibited sorption and desorption behaviour comparable to that of conventional wood-based composites (Wu 1999). The highest sorption hysteresis was observed in the untreated reference samples, while the lowest hysteresis was found in glycerol-treated MBB made from pistachio nutshells (Figure 3A-B). Glycerol-treated samples generally reached a lower equilibrium moisture content than their untreated counterparts. Furthermore, the glycerol treatment led to a flattening of the

sorption/desorption isotherms, suggesting a modified interaction between the material and ambient humidity caused by the blocking of free hydroxyl groups, which corresponds to already published studies (Essoua et al. 2016; Appels et al. 2020). A negative change in mass during desorption was observed in the glycerol-treated samples. This behaviour is caused by residual ME in the MBB samples and can be explained by hydrate formation (Scholl and Schmidt 2014).

Figure 3 Sorption (A) and desorption (B) curves of mycelium-based composites

Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Glycerol-treated walnut MBB exhibited the highest stiffness, both storage modulus and loss modulus were highest in comparison with other MBB variants (Figure 4A-B). This behaviour is given by high mechanical properties of walnut shells (Kaupp and Naimi-Jamal 2011). Glycerol treatment increased the difference in storage and loss moduli between MBB variants. Whereas the values are comparable for W0 and P0, after glycerol treatment, the difference is substantially higher. This suggests that the type of filler material plays a key role in the performance of the described MBB. In contrast, reference samples without nutshells reached the lowest storage and loss moduli, highlighting the reinforcing effect of nutshell incorporation. Previous research has reported that nutshell particles, due to their high lignin content, contribute significantly to stiffness in biocomposites (Sutivisedsak et al. 2012). It must be noted that although mechanical data from reference samples without filler (R0 and RG) are presented, these should be interpreted only as qualitative benchmarks. Due to their structure and lack of lignocellulosic particles, they are not structurally equivalent to the nutshell-based MBBs, and any direct mechanical comparison must be treated with caution.

For all nutshell-based MBB samples, the storage modulus decreased with increasing temperature, which is characteristic of thermosetting and viscoelastic bio-based composites (Kumar et al. 2024). This behaviour may be attributed not only to their layered structure resulting from sample preparation, but also to differences in chemical composition. Unlike nutshell-based MBBs, the reference samples lack lignin and hemicelluloses, which are known to undergo softening and degradation within this temperature range (Kelley et al. 1987; Kalita et al. 2015). Instead, the main constituent of reference samples is fungal mycelium, which contains chitin, a highly crystalline polysaccharide with thermal behaviour more similar to cellulose (Kumirska et al. 2010). This compositional difference may result in reduced thermal relaxation and contribute to the distinct stiffness-temperature profile observed. The loss factor is slightly increasing with increasing temperature for all walnut and pistachio samples till 160°C, and then a rapid increase is observed, which also corresponds to changes measured by STA.

Figure 4 Dynamic mechanical analysis of MBB, effect of temperature on storage modulus E' (A), effect of temperature on loss modulus E'' (B), effect of temperature on loss factor $\tan \delta$ (C)

Shore Hardness

The Shore A hardness results (presented in Table 2) align with the findings from DMA, further confirming the effect of both filler type and glycerol treatment on the mechanical performance of the developed MBB. All tested MBBs fall within the range of medium-hard materials. The walnut MBB exhibited the highest Shore A hardness. Among them, the glycerol-treated walnut MBB showed the highest hardness overall. The difference in hardness between the glycerol-treated walnut MBB and the pistachio MBB is statistically significant at the 0.05 significance level. These results are consistent with the DMA findings, where walnut MBBs also demonstrated superior stiffness. It has to be noted that thanks to the incorporation of nutshell filler, the hardness of the developed MBB is substantially higher than the hardness of the

conventional MBB samples produced by solid-state fermentation from other lignocellulosic sources (Schultz et al. 2024).

To better contextualise these differences, Shore A hardness was also measured on the raw nutshells. Walnut shells exhibited a Shore A hardness of 79.8 ± 2.32 , while pistachio shells reached a higher value of 95.1 ± 1.58 . This indicates that pistachio shells are intrinsically harder than walnut shells. Interestingly, despite the higher raw hardness of pistachio shells, the walnut-based MBBs achieved higher hardness values. This inverse trend suggests that the mechanical performance of the MBBs is not determined solely by the inherent hardness of the filler material but also by factors such as interfacial bonding, composite homogeneity, and the internal structure. This effect is well known in the composite structure theory (Kiran et al. 2018). The lower hardness of pistachio-based MBBs may be related to poorer bonding with the fungal matrix.

Table 2 Shore hardness of the produced MBB

Variant	WG	W0	PG	P0	RG	R0
Shore A	71.4 (4.08)	67.8 (3.22)	65.67 (2.87)	63.80 (2.23)	-	-

Note: values in brackets are standard deviations, it was not possible to measure the hardness of the reference samples due to the thickness

Simultaneous Thermal Analysis

The main parameters derived from the thermogravimetric analysis are summarized in Table 3, while the corresponding TG, DTG, and DSC curves are shown in Figure 5. The residual mass of all samples lies within the range of 20–30 wt%, which is typical for nutshells and lignocellulosic materials in general (Noszczyk et al. 2021). Samples treated with glycerol exhibit a lower residual mass. This behaviour is expected, as glycerol undergoes almost complete thermal decomposition by 600 °C, and similarly reduced residues have been reported for glycerol-treated lignocellulosic systems (Mahmood et al. 2021). Consequently, glycerol treatment does not result in an increased char yield or enhanced thermal stability at

elevated temperatures. The addition of glycerol introduces an additional degradation step prior to the main thermal decomposition of the MBBs, occurring between approximately 150 °C and 250 °C. Comparable low-temperature decomposition steps associated with glycerol have been reported previously (Dou et al. 2009; Hilal-AINaqbi et al. 2016). While both reference variants show minor mass loss in this temperature range, the glycerol-treated samples exhibit a markedly higher mass loss. Since hemicelluloses are known to thermally decompose within a similar temperature interval, an overlap of glycerol-related degradation and hemicellulose decomposition cannot be excluded (Yang et al. 2006; Noszczyk et al. 2021).

In the DSC curves of the developed MBB, weak exothermic features are observed between 150 °C and 250 °C. Under inert conditions, such signals can arise from overlapping endothermic bond-cleavage reactions and exothermic secondary processes, including dehydration, condensation, and early char-forming reactions, as described for lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis (Shafizadeh 1982; Antal and Grønli 2003). In the reference samples, where decomposition processes also occur in this temperature range, overlapping or compensating thermal effects may lead to less distinct calorimetric features. The TG and DTG curves of the nutshell-containing composites exhibit a characteristic lignocellulosic decomposition pattern associated with the main biomass constituents, namely hemicelluloses, cellulose, and lignin (Yang et al. 2006). An additional mass-loss peak preceding the main lignocellulosic decomposition peak is observed and can be associated with the presence of mycelium in the composite, consistent with reported thermal degradation behaviour of mycelium-based materials (Jones et al. 2018). Thermogravimetric analysis further shows that glycerol treatment shifts the decomposition peaks to higher temperatures in both the nutshell-based composites and the reference samples, in agreement with literature reporting modified degradation pathways and altered thermal kinetics in glycerol-plasticized biopolymer systems (Mahmood et al. 2021; Suyatma et al. 2005).

Exothermic events observed during thermal decomposition are characteristic of lignin-containing biomass under inert conditions and are commonly attributed to secondary

condensation and char-forming reactions (Yang et al. 2007; Shafizadeh 1982). In the reference material, distinct DSC features merge into a single, more intense peak upon glycerol addition, indicating a modification of the decomposition pathway and increased overlap of reaction steps, as reported for glycerol-affected pyrolysis systems and plasticized biopolymers (Dou et al. 2009; Mahmood et al. 2021). The mycelium-based materials exhibit two pronounced DSC features, which are attributed to overlapping contributions from the lignocellulosic substrate and the mycelial fraction. Although a strict separation of individual reaction steps is not possible, comparable underlying pyrolytic mechanisms can be inferred from the corresponding temperature ranges (Yang et al. 2006). Compared to the lignocellulosic reference without mycelium, these features are shifted towards higher temperatures and become broader, which is consistent with the higher charring tendency and structural complexity of mycelium-containing composites reported in the literature (Jones et al. 2018; Jones et al. 2020).

Table 3 Main variables determined from STA measurements

Variant	Onset (°C)	Residual	DTG	DTG	MLR 1 (%/min)	MLR 2 (%/min)	DSC	DSC
		Mass (%)	Peak 1 (°C)	Peak 2 (°C)			Peak 1 (°C)	Peak 2 (°C)
R0	264.3	31.2	299.8	-	-5.38	-	268.5	305.3
RG	285.1	28.0	306.9	-	-8.04	-	308.2	-
W0	260.2	29.2	287.2	336.1	-4.91	-6.49	287.8	341.8
WG	272.5	25.6	300.6	354.6	-4.49	-6.23	300.6	363.5
P0	250.5	29.9	281.5	335.1	-4.89	-7.38	279.6	339.9
PG	274.5	21.2	294.1	357.7	-6.73	-7.31	296.7	412

Table 4 Temperatures of the initial onset, the main onset, and the mass loss in-between

	1st Onset (°C)	Main Onset (°C)	Mass Loss in-between (%)
R0	149.5	255.5	-9.4
RG	140.7	284.1	-17.0
W0	-	-	-
WG	147.5	271.9	-13.8
P0	-	-	-
PG	139.3	267.6	-9.9

Figure 5 TG, DTG and DSC curves of the mycelium-based composites, exothermic reactions are represented by positive heat-flow values.

Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy

The FT-IR spectra of the reference pure fungi materials (RO, RG) showed bands attributed to β -chitin: the strong amide I band at 1645 cm^{-1} and high intensity skeletal C-O-C stretching bands around 1032 cm^{-1} (Fig. 6, black spectra) (Kumirska et al. 2010). Although glycerol

treatment led to changes in the mechanical and sorption behaviour of the MBBs, distinct glycerol-related bands were not detected in the FT-IR spectra. This is due to spectral overlap with the major components of the composite. Glycerol's characteristic O–H stretching vibration ($3280\text{--}3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$) coincides with the broad O–H bands of cellulose, hemicellulose, and chitin. Similarly, its C–O stretching vibrations ($1030\text{--}1080\text{ cm}^{-1}$) overlap with C–O and C–O–C bands from polysaccharides and fungal glucans (Kumirska et al. 2010). Lignin's aromatic skeletal vibrations ($1510\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the C–H bending modes ($\sim 1375\text{ cm}^{-1}$) also contribute to masking of glycerol-specific signals (Faix 1991). Additionally, part of the glycerol may have been evaporated during drying, reducing its detectability by FT-IR. Therefore, based on the FT-IR evidence and in line with previous studies (Mali et al. 2006; Sanyang et al. 2016), we interpret the role of glycerol in our system as primarily that of a surface modifier and plasticiser. In all walnut and pistachio composites the bands related to chitin were mixed with typical bands for ligno-cellulosic materials. An acetyl group (C=O vibration) attributed to hemicelluloses was found at 1733 cm^{-1} and an aromatic stretching vibration typical for lignin around 1505 cm^{-1} (Faix 1991). Based on the band intensity of the latter one we can conclude on lower lignin content in pistachio (P0, PG, blue spectra) than in walnut shell composites (WO, WG). This is in agreement with former spectroscopic results (Xiao et al. 2021) and chemical analysis pointing up to 50-% lignin of the total weight of the fruit (Zhao et al. 2019, Morales et al. 2022). The higher lignin content in walnut shell composites could explain the higher shore hardness.

Figure 6 FT-IR spectra of MBB variants

Scanning Electron Microscopy

SEM confirmed the hypothesis that filtration of the liquid culture, consisting of mycelium and ground nutshells in malt extract, resulted in a composite structure formed by lignocellulosic particles interconnected with fungal hyphae (Figure 7A–D). On the surfaces of the composites that were exposed to air, a continuous fungal skin was developed (Figure 7B). As previously reported, the fungal skin can provide additional functions, as regular coating of materials (Appels et al. 2020; Hýsek et al. 2023). Ground walnut and pistachio shells were visibly bound together by hyphae, forming a porous and interconnected network (Figure 7A, C, D). While individual hyphae are not always visible due to their aggregation into denser mycelial networks,

Figure 7A, C, D shows continuous contact between fungal mycelium and the ground shells, supporting the presence of effective binding zones. The dense presence of fungal material is consistent with FTIR results indicating a high chitin and polysaccharide content. No significant structural differences were observed using SEM between untreated and glycerol-treated samples, suggesting that the glycerol treatment did not affect the morphology of the composite at the microscale. To further examine the possible effect of glycerol on the composite microstructure, an additional EDX analysis was performed on both treated and untreated fractured MBB samples. In untreated samples, Na, K, Cl, O, and C were detected as statistically significant elements. In contrast, the glycerol-treated samples showed only carbon and oxygen as statistically significant elements. This suggests that inorganic minerals were leached during the glycerol treatment. Given the highly topographic and porous nature of the MBB surfaces, no exact quantitative analysis was conducted, and these results are presented as indicative. The elemental composition analysis showed that the carbon and oxygen content in the glycerol-treated samples exceeded 99%, whereas in the untreated samples it was slightly lower, with carbon and oxygen accounting for more than 97% of the total detected elements.

The results of our study align with recent trends in hybrid bio-based composites, where synergistic effects between LC particles and mineral fillers (e.g. CaCO_3 , talc) are explored to tailor mechanical and thermal performance. Although the present MBBs were produced without mineral additives, the integration of such components, as suggested by Karagöz et al. (2025a, 2025b), may offer further optimisation potential for future formulations. The mechanical performance of the produced MBBs is strongly influenced by both the chemical composition and cell morphology of the lignocellulosic fillers. Walnut shells, which led to the highest Shore A hardness and stiffness, are characterised by a higher lignin content. Lignin, a rigid and cross-linked aromatic polymer, enhances the stiffness and dimensional stability of LC materials, thus contributing to the mechanical reinforcement of the composite matrix (Karagöz et al. 2025a; Karagöz et al. 2025b). Additionally, the interlocking puzzle-like geometry of polylobate cells in

nutshells increases particle contact area and mechanical interlocking, providing an effective scaffold for fungal hyphae. This promotes improved particle binding and network formation within the composite. These findings highlight the synergistic influence of bioprocess design, particle chemistry, and microstructure on the functional properties of bio-based composites.

Figure 7 Structure of created composites and input particles; cross section of PG sample (A), cross section of the surface of PG sample (B), structure of breached W0 sample (C), cross section of WG sample (D), ground pistachio nutshells (E), ground walnut nutshells (F).

4. Conclusion

This study demonstrated the fabrication of MBBs reinforced with ground walnut and pistachio nutshells using a combination of liquid- and solid-state fermentation. The applied process enabled effective binding of lignocellulosic particles by *Ganoderma sessile* without synthetic adhesives, resulting in self-binding composite structures. The type of nutshell filler and post-treatment with glycerol significantly influenced the properties of the materials. Walnut-based MBBs outperformed pistachio-based variants in mechanical performance, with the glycerol-treated walnut composite achieving the highest Shore A hardness and exhibiting the best stiffness and thermal stability characteristics. Moisture-related properties were also improved. DVS measurements showed that glycerol-treated MBBs had a lower equilibrium moisture content and a reduction in sorption hysteresis. FTIR spectra confirmed compositional differences, particularly higher lignin signals in walnut-based samples and strong chitin-related bands across all variants. SEM imaging revealed a uniform composite morphology, with no structural degradation due to glycerol treatment, and the presence of a fungal skin layer on surfaces exposed to air. These results demonstrate that nutshells are viable fillers for MBBs and that biotechnological approaches, such as combined-state fermentation, can be applied to engineer mechanically reinforced bio-composites for sustainable applications. Our findings establish a foundation for understanding structure-property relationships in MBBs fabricated via a hybrid fermentation process. While this study focused on fundamental material characterisation, it demonstrated the ability to bind LC particles without synthetic adhesives and opens a pathway for sustainable production via a novel biotechnology procedure.

The materials developed show potential for future use in non-load-bearing applications such as thermal or acoustic insulation, biodegradable packaging, or interior design elements. However, several limitations must be acknowledged. Comprehensive mechanical testing was not performed due to specimen brittleness and geometry. Bulk density was not quantified using standard volumetric methods, and areal density was used for comparison of thin samples. Quantitative chemical fractionation of lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose was not conducted,

and FTIR analysis remained qualitative due to the dominance of fungal signals. Glycerol uptake was not quantified because the simultaneous leaching of residual ME prevented the calculation of mass gain. Future work should address mechanical optimisation, quantitative compositional analysis, and process refinement toward scale-up.

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5. References

Aiduang, W., Chanthaluck, A., Kumla, J., Jatuwong, K., Srinuanpan, S., Waroonkun, T., ... & Suwannarach, N. (2022). Amazing fungi for eco-friendly composite materials: A comprehensive review. *Journal of Fungi*, 8(8), 842.

Alaneme, K. K., Anaele, J. U., Oke, T. M., Kareem, S. A., Adediran, M., Ajibuwa, O. A., & Anabaranze, Y. O. (2023). Mycelium based composites: A review of their bio-fabrication procedures, material properties and potential for green building and construction applications. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 83, 234-250.

Antal, M. J., & Grønli, M. (2003). The art, science, and technology of charcoal production. *Industrial & engineering chemistry research*, 42(8), 1619-1640.

Antreich, S. J., Xiao, N., Huss, J. C., Horbelt, N., Eder, M., Weinkamer, R., & Gierlinger, N. (2019). The puzzle of the walnut shell: a novel cell type with interlocked packing. *Advanced Science*, 6(16), 1900644.

Appels, F. V., Camere, S., Montalti, M., Karana, E., Jansen, K. M., Dijksterhuis, J., ... & Wösten, H. A. (2019). Fabrication factors influencing mechanical, moisture-and water-related properties of mycelium-based composites. *Materials & Design*, 161, 64-71.

Appels, F. V., Dijksterhuis, J., Lukasiewicz, C. E., Jansen, K. M., Wösten, H. A., & Krijgheld, P. (2018). Hydrophobin gene deletion and environmental growth conditions impact mechanical properties of mycelium by affecting the density of the material. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 4703.

Appels, F. V., van den Brandhof, J. G., Dijksterhuis, J., de Kort, G. W., & Wösten, H. A. (2020). Fungal mycelium classified in different material families based on glycerol treatment. *Communications Biology*, 3(1), 334.

Attias, N., Danai, O., Abitbol, T., Tarazi, E., Ezov, N., Pereman, I., & Grobman, Y. J. (2020). Mycelium bio-composites in industrial design and architecture: Comparative review and experimental analysis. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 246, 119037.

Cerimi, K., Akkaya, K. C., Pohl, C., Schmidt, B., & Neubauer, P. (2019). Fungi as source for new bio-based materials: a patent review. *Fungal biology and biotechnology*, 6, 1-10.

Dong, C., Davies, I. J., Fornari Junior, C. C. M., & Scaffaro, R. (2017). Mechanical properties of Macadamia nutshell powder and PLA bio-composites. *Australian Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 15(3), 150-156.

Dou, B., Dupont, V., Williams, P. T., Chen, H., & Ding, Y. (2009). Thermogravimetric kinetics of crude glycerol. *Bioresource technology*, 100(9), 2613-2620.

Elsacker, E., Søndergaard, A., Van Wylick, A., Peeters, E., & De Laet, L. (2021). Growing living and multifunctional mycelium composites for large-scale formwork applications using robotic abrasive wire-cutting. *Construction and Building Materials*, 283, 122732.

Elsacker, E., Vandelook, S., Van Wylick, A., Ruytinx, J., De Laet, L., & Peeters, E. (2020). A comprehensive framework for the production of mycelium-based lignocellulosic composites. *Science of The Total Environment*, 725, 138431.

Essoua, G. G., Blanchet, P., Landry, V., & Beauregard, R. (2016). Pine wood treated with a citric acid and glycerol mixture: Biomaterial performance improved by a bio-byproduct. *BioResources*, 11(2), 3049-3072.

Faix, O. (1991). Classification of lignins from different botanical origins by FT-IR spectroscopy. *Holzforschung* 45, 21–27. doi: 10.1515/hfsg.1991.45.s1.21

Gajdačová, P., Hýsek, Š., & Jarský, V. (2018). Utilisation of winter rapeseed in wood-based materials as a solution of wood shortage and forest protection. *BioResources*, 13(2), 2546-2561.

Ghazvinian, A., Farrokhsiar, P., Vieira, F., Pecchia, J., & Gursoy, B. (2019). Mycelium-based bio-composites for architecture: Assessing the effects of cultivation factors on compressive strength. *Mater. Res. Innov*, 2, 505-514.

Hilal-AlNaqbi, A., Al-Omari, S. B., & Selim, M. Y. (2016). Assessment of tree leaves flakes mixed with crude glycerol as a bioenergy source. *BioMed Research International*, 2016(1), 5805806.

Huss, J. C., & Gierlinger, N. (2021). Functional packaging of seeds. *New Phytologist*, 230(6), 2154-2163.

Huss, J. C., Antreich, S. J., Bachmayr, J., Xiao, N., Eder, M., Konnerth, J., & Gierlinger, N. (2020). Topological interlocking and geometric stiffening as complementary strategies for strong plant shells. *Advanced Materials*, 32(48), 2004519.

Hýsek, Š., Daňková, M., Jozífek, M., Němec, M., & Wimmer, R. (2023). Mycelium-based biocomposites from recycled wood: influence of fungal species on properties of biocomposites. Proceedings of the 32th International Conference on Wood Science and Technology - ICWST 2023 "UNLEASHING THE POTENTIAL OF WOOD-BASED MATERIALS", 83–89. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10952318>

Hýsek, Š., Wimmer, R., & Böhm, M. (2016). Optimal processing of flax and hemp fibre nonwovens. *BioResources*, 11(4), 8522-8534.

Jones, M., Bhat, T., Kandare, E., Thomas, A., Joseph, P., Dekiwadia, C., ... & Wang, C. H. (2018). Thermal degradation and fire properties of fungal mycelium and mycelium-biomass composite materials. *Scientific reports*, 8(1), 17583.

Jones, M., Mautner, A., Luenco, S., Bismarck, A., & John, S. (2020). Engineered mycelium composite construction materials from fungal biorefineries: A critical review. *Materials & Design*, 187, 108397.

Kalita, D., & Netravali, A. N. (2015). Interfaces in green composites: a critical review. *Reviews of Adhesion and Adhesives*, 3(4), 386-443.

Karagöz, İ., Duyar, H. İ., Çavuşoğlu, A., & Sepetcioglu, H. (2025a). Synergistic Effects on the Mechanical, Thermal, and Morphological Properties of HDPE Composites Reinforced With Walnut Shell and Nano-Calcium Carbonate. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, e57464.

Karagöz, İ., Ocak, I. A., Çavuşoğlu, A., & Sepetçioglu, H. (2025b). Advancing sustainable materials: characterization of pistachio shell and talc filled polyester composites. *Colloid and Polymer Science*, 1-16.

Karagöz, İ., Tamer, İ. M., Çavuşoğlu, A., & Sepetcioglu, H. (2024). Investigation of mechanical, thermal, and morphological properties of walnut shell and nano clay reinforced HDPE composites. *Materials Today Communications*, 41, 110905.

Kaupp, G., & Naimi-Jamal, M. R. (2011). Nutshells' mechanical response: from nanoindentation and structure to bionics models. *Journal of Materials Chemistry*, 21(23), 8389-8400.

Kelley, S. S., Rials, T. G., & Glasser, W. G. (1987). Relaxation behaviour of the amorphous components of wood. *Journal of materials science*, 22(2), 617-624.

Kiran, M. D., Govindaraju, H. K., Jayaraju, T., & Kumar, N. (2018). Effect of fillers on mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites. *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 5(10), 22421-22424.

Kumar, S. S., Vignesh, V., Prasad, V. V. S. H., Sunil, B. D. Y., Srinivas, R., Sanjay, M. R., & Siengchin, S. (2024). Static and dynamic mechanical analysis of hybrid natural fibre composites for engineering applications. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 14(13), 14889-14901.

Kumirska, J., Czerwicka, M., Kaczyński, Z., Bychowska, A., Brzozowski, K., Thöming, J., & Stepnowski, P. (2010). Application of spectroscopic methods for structural analysis of chitin and chitosan. *Marine drugs*, 8(5), 1567-1636.

Madusanka, C., Udayanga, D., Nilmini, R., Rajapaksha, S., Hewawasam, C., Manamgoda, D., & Vasco-Correa, J. (2024). A review of recent advances in fungal mycelium based composites. *Discover Materials*, 4(1), 13.

Mahmood, H., Mehmood, S., Shakeel, A., Iqbal, T., Kazmi, M. A., Khurram, A. R., & Moniruzzaman, M. (2021). Glycerol assisted pretreatment of lignocellulose wheat straw materials as a promising approach for fabrication of sustainable fibrous filler for biocomposites. *Polymers*, 13(3), 388.

Mali, S., Grossmann, M. V. E., García, M. A., Martino, M. N., & Zaritzky, N. E. (2006). Effects of controlled storage on thermal, mechanical and barrier properties of plasticized films from different starch sources. *Journal of food engineering*, 75(4), 453-460.

Morales Matías, A., Labidi Bouchrika, J., & Gullón Estévez, P. (2022). Integral valorisation of walnut shells based on a three-step sequential delignification. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 310.

Muiruri, J. K., Chuan Yeo, J. C., Zhu, Q., Ye, E., Loh, X. J., & Li, Z. (2023). Sustainable mycelium-bound biocomposites: design strategies, materials properties, and emerging applications. *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering*, 11(18), 6801-6821.

Němec, M., Prokúpek, L., Lexa, M., Janesch, J., & Hýsek, Š. (2025). Cold-pressed hybrid lignin composite reinforced with beech and spruce wood for automotive applications. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 234, 121561.

Noszczyk, T., Dyjakon, A., & Koziel, J. A. (2021). Kinetic parameters of nut shells pyrolysis. *Energies*, 14(3), 682.

Şahin, A. E., Fidan, S., Çetin, B., & Sınmazçelik, T. (2024). Comparison of the usage of nut shell, walnut shell, and pistachio shell as a reinforcement particle on the mechanical and wear performance of polypropylene. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 141(16), e55248.

Sandak, A. (2023). Engineered living materials for sustainable and resilient architecture. *Nature Reviews Materials*, 8(6), 357-359.

Sanyang, M. L., Sapuan, S. M., Jawaid, M., Ishak, M. R., & Sahari, J. (2016). Effect of plasticizer type and concentration on physical properties of biodegradable films based on sugar palm (*Arenga pinnata*) starch for food packaging. *Journal of food science and technology*, 53(1), 326-336.

Sayfutdinova, A. R., Cherednichenko, K. A., Rakitina, M. A., Dubinich, V. N., Bardina, K. A., Rubtsova, M. I., ... & Voronin, D. V. (2023). Natural Fibrous Materials Based on Fungal Mycelium Hyphae as Porous Supports for Shape-Stable Phase-Change Composites. *Polymers*, 15(23), 4504.

- Scholl, S. K., & Schmidt, S. J. (2014). Determining the mechanism and parameters of hydrate formation and loss in glucose. *Journal of food science*, 79(11), E2232-E2244.
- Schultz, N., Fazli, A., Piros, S., Barranco-Origel, Y., DeLa Cruz, P., & Schneider, D. Y. (2024). Characterization of mycelium biocomposites under simulated weathering conditions. *ACS Applied Bio Materials*, 7(12), 8408-8422.
- Sepet, H., Aydemir, B., & Tarakcioglu, N. (2020). Evaluation of mechanical and thermal properties and creep behavior of micro-and nano-CaCO₃ particle-filled HDPE nano-and microcomposites produced in large scale. *Polymer Bulletin*, 77(7), 3677-3695.
- Sepetcioglu, H., Demet, S. M., Karagöz, İ., & Bagci, M. (2025). Solid Particle Erosion Behaviors of Walnut Shell-Filled Acrylic-Styrene-Acrylate (ASA) and Polycarbonate/Acrylic-Styrene-Acrylate (PC/ASA) Thermoplastic Blend Biocomposites. *Polymer Composites*.
- Shafizadeh, F. (1982). Introduction to pyrolysis of biomass. *Journal of analytical and applied pyrolysis*, 3(4), 283-305.
- Sun, W., Tajvidi, M., Hunt, C. G., McIntyre, G., & Gardner, D. J. (2019). Fully bio-based hybrid composites made of wood, fungal mycelium and cellulose nanofibrils. *Scientific reports*, 9(1), 3766.
- Sutivisedsak, N., Cheng, H. N., Burks, C. S., Johnson, J. A., Siegel, J. P., Civerolo, E. L., & Biswas, A. (2012). Use of nutshells as fillers in polymer composites. *Journal of Polymers and the Environment*, 20, 305-314.
- Suyatma, N. E., Tighzert, L., Copinet, A., & Coma, V. (2005). Effects of hydrophilic plasticizers on mechanical, thermal, and surface properties of chitosan films. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 53(10), 3950-3957.
- Sydor, M., Bonenberg, A., Doczekalska, B., & Cofta, G. (2021). Mycelium-based composites in art, architecture, and interior design: a review. *Polymers*, 14(1), 145.

- Wu, Q. (1999). Application of Nelson's sorption isotherm to wood composites and overlays. *Wood and Fiber Science*, 187-191.
- Xiao, N., Felhofer, M., Antreich, S. J., Huss, J. C., Mayer, K., Singh, A., ... & Gierlinger, N. (2021). Twist and lock: nutshell structures for high strength and energy absorption. *Royal Society Open Science*, 8(8), 210399.
- Yang, H., Yan, R., Chen, H., Lee, D. H., & Zheng, C. (2007). Characteristics of hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin pyrolysis. *Fuel*, 86(12-13), 1781-1788.
- Yang, H., Yan, R., Chen, H., Zheng, C., Lee, D. H., & Liang, D. T. (2006). In-depth investigation of biomass pyrolysis based on three major components: hemicellulose, cellulose and lignin. *Energy & fuels*, 20(1), 388-393.
- Zhang, W., Xu, J., & Yu, T. X. (2022). Dynamic behaviors of bio-inspired structures: Design, mechanisms, and models. *Engineering Structures*, 265, 114490.
- Zhao, S., Niu, J., Yun, L., Liu, K., Wang, S., Wen, J., ... & Zhang, Z. (2019). The relationship among the structural, cellular, and physical properties of walnut shells. *HortScience*, 54(2), 275-281.